

Pedestrian Simulation in SUMO Through Externally Modelled Agents

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ABSTRACT

Pedestrian simulation is often forgotten or implemented poorly in most high-profile traffic simulators. This is the case of SUMO, where pedestrian models are very simple and not based in real human behaviour, making it impossible to study pedestrian safety with it. With this in mind, the ability to externally control pedestrians in SUMO was explored. Using Unity3D to create an external 3D representation of a running SUMO simulation, we were able to create and control pedestrians through the TraCI API. This also opened the possibility to use virtual reality immersed subjects to participate in the simulation, opening the door to study real pedestrian behaviour to create more elaborate models. It also allowed us to completely offload the pedestrian simulation from SUMO to Unity3D, which was tested with the external implementation of the social forces model, without losing SUMO's interactions between pedestrians and motorized vehicles.

INTRODUCTION

Pedestrians are the smallest, lightest, slowest and least protected road users. Also being the ones with the most movement freedom makes them the most vulnerable (Yannis et al. 2011). Despite pedestrian mortality being on decline, 5320 fatalities were registered in 2016 in the European Union alone, making up 21% of all road fatalities (European Commission 2018).

Traffic simulators have been used to study the flow of traffic at least since 1955 (Pursula 1999). Through the years they have evolved to use better simulation paradigms, better models and eventually cover whole traffic networks instead of specific locations. A direct application of these simulators is to study road safety conditions (Young et al. 2014).

Although pedestrians are the most vulnerable road users, their inclusion in traffic simulators is not always

guaranteed. Even in cases where they are represented, they are not always modelled with the care and finesse of the motorized cohabitants. This is the case of the traffic simulator SUMO, an open-source microscopic traffic simulation package first released in 2002 (Behrisch et al. 2011). It is one of the most popular traffic simulator for research, second only to VISSIM in terms of number of published papers that make use of it (Mubasher and Jaffry 2015). Despite its popularity, it was only in 2014 that SUMO included pedestrian modelling in its package, 12 years after its initial release (Krajzewicz et al. 2014; Erdmann and Krajzewicz 2015). This model, called stripping model, was developed to fit SUMO developers requirements, which focused on enabling vehicle-pedestrian interactions and how the flow of pedestrians affects traffic flow (Erdmann and Krajzewicz 2015).

In the current model, the sidewalks and crosswalks are split in several lanes, akin to lanes on a multi-lane road. Pedestrians can move to adjacent lanes to prevent being stuck behind a slower pedestrian or to avoid a collision with another pedestrian head on (Krajzewicz et al. 2014; Erdmann and Krajzewicz 2015). This model, while efficient, is not the best at representing pedestrian behavior. In the real world, pedestrians don't move in lanes like cars do, don't always walk in their designated areas and might attempt to cross the road in places other than the crosswalk, or when the crosswalk signal indicates not to cross. These oversights limit the impact of pedestrian safety research made in SUMO.

Currently, the simulation information generated by SUMO can be used by an external application through the use of TraCI (Traffic Control Interface). This API (Application Programming Interface) also allows real-time manipulation of simulation states and variables, enabling the control of vehicles through the interface. Currently, TraCI supports the free movement of vehicles, while for pedestrians it is not specified in SUMO's documentation whether this is possible or not. This means that it currently might not be possible to implement new pedestrian models, without direct manipulation of the source code.

The main goal of this work is to improve SUMO's ability to integrate improved pedestrian models, without the need of tampering with its source code. To achieve this, a communication interface between SUMO

and Unity3D was developed to create a 1:1 representation of the simulated world and its inhabitant in Unity3D, where models can be developed and applied to pedestrians. Another goal is to allow people to control a pedestrian in the simulation with the objective of studying their behaviour to further improve the used models. The contributions of this work are:

- Facilitate creating pedestrian models in SUMO.
- Simplify the integration of these external pedestrian models in SUMO.
- Allow real people to control a pedestrian in SUMO to study pedestrian safety in a danger-free environment.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. In Section *Traffic Simulators*, a review of popular traffic and pedestrian simulators is made, with special attention to SUMO. This is followed by Section *Related Work* which presents similar research. Section *Methodology* documents the approach of the solution, including its architecture along with the tools and models used. The details for the implementation following the proposed solution can be found in Section *Implementation - Platform and Systems* and *Implementation - Pedestrian Model*. Section *Results and Analysis* presents the results of the experiments and their discussion. Finally, Section *Conclusion and Future Work* ends the article with a conclusion of the developed work and ideas for future improvements.

TRAFFIC SIMULATORS

Currently, several traffic simulators with different features are readily available, some being available commercially, and others being free to use and open source. Some surveys about the state of the art of traffic simulators were published in the past decade, providing useful information on the capabilities of different simulators and in some cases, performance comparisons.

In 2009, a review of traffic simulation software compared six of the top platforms of the time (Kotusevski and Hawick 2009). The authors created a list of criteria that would be used as the comparison basis, containing: Licensing model; Platform portability; Documentation/UI; Creation of traffic networks; Outputs; Large network simulation; and computational performance.

More recently, an update version of the previous study was published in 2017 (Ejercito et al. 2017). It followed the same comparison criteria, but with a reduced number of platforms, of which two were present in the 2009 review, and the other two were new.

A systematic literature review on traffic flow simulators was also conducted and published in 2015 (Mubasher and Jaffry 2015). A list of 15 traffic simulators used in all types of research is presented, of which 5 were isolated for being the ones more frequently used in the studied literature.

Table I summarizes the investigated traffic simulators in the mentioned surveys. It becomes evident that there is a lot of overlap and that some of the platforms used 10 years ago are still relevant today, one of which is SUMO, the platform that is the target of this project.

TABLE I: Summary of traffic simulators discussed in each literature review: Kotusevski and Hawick 2009 (1); Mubasher and Jaffry 2015 (2); and Ejercito et al. 2017 (3). Column "Peds?" indicates the presence of pedestrian simulation, and "OSS" whether or not it is open-source software.

Simulator	Peds?	OSS?	(1)	(2)	(3)
SUMO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PARAMICS	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
Treiber's Microsimulator	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
AIMSUN	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Trafficware SimTraff	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
CORSIM	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
VISSIM	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
MatSim	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓

SUMO

SUMO is an open-source, free to use, microscopic traffic simulation package with several articles published documenting its development and progress. In (Behrisch et al. 2011), a general overview of the package is found. Despite being an old publication, it still reflects the current architecture and basic functionality of current SUMO versions.

More recently, pedestrian modeling has been implemented in SUMO, a feature that it had been lacking when compared to some of its alternatives like VISSIM and AIMSUN. Two papers report the development of this feature, an earlier one from 2014 overviews the implementation of pedestrians and bicycle traffic (Krajzewicz et al. 2014), and a more detailed one published in 2015 about the process of modelling pedestrians in SUMO (Erdmann and Krajzewicz 2015).

Currently SUMO offers two simulation options for pedestrians, the "nonInteracting" and the "striping" models. As the name suggests, in the "nonInteracting" model the pedestrians walk at constant speed, don't interact with each other or with vehicles, and teleport across intersections. It is recommended to use this model when pedestrian dynamics are not essential.

The striping model is a big step up from the previous model, as it enables pedestrian-pedestrian and pedestrian-vehicle interactions. For this model to work properly, the layout of road infrastructure used by pedestrians must be modelled. In this implementation, 3 distinct zones exclusive to pedestrians exist, visible in the color-coded Fig. 1: sidewalk (grey), crossings (zebra) and walking areas (blue). When pedestrians move in the sidewalk or crossing, they follow a striping formation, akin to the way vehicles follow lanes on the road. These areas are split in different lanes in which the pedestrians can move along. If they find an obstacle or a slower pedestrian in their lane they can move to another adjacent one and proceed. In walking areas, which serve as a connection patch between sidewalks and crossings, pedestrians follow a predetermined trajectory calculated at the beginning of the simulation.

Fig. 1: Pedestrian network model in SUMO (Krajewicz et al. 2014)

RELATED WORK

As mentioned before, the main objective of this work is to enable external pedestrian models to be connected to SUMO via the TraCI API and incorporate this system in Unity3D to be able to create a 3D version of the network used in SUMO. With this in mind, a literature search was made using the terms 'SUMO', 'TraCI', 'Pedestrian' and 'Unity' in different combinations.

The earliest publication found mentioning a connection between SUMO and Unity3D dates back to 2014, to create a platform for faster, safer and cheaper testing of ADAS (Advanced Driving Assistance Systems) using simulated environments (J. S. V. Gonçalves et al. 2014). This implementation used SUMO as a central server that provides information to remaining modules, including the IC-DEEP simulator (J. Gonçalves et al. 2012). This simulator is based in Unity3D and was developed to test safety aspects of IVIS (In-Vehicle Information Systems).

The work mentioned above then served as the basis to a project funded by the Austrian Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology (BMVIT) that focuses on researching vehicle to vehicle and vehicle to pedestrian communications to study systems related to pedestrian safety. To create a platform for this type of communications, SUMO was used in conjunction with Unity3D to create a user interactable microscopic driving simulation. This was first used to create a Traffic Light Assistant system for drivers (Olaverri-Monreal et al. 2018). This work was later expanded to receive data from the pedestrian locations to warn the driver of their position when a danger situation was detected (Artal-Villa and Olaverri-Monreal 2019). This research was later validated by studying the behaviour of 20 subjects driving in the simulated environment with and without the help from the system (Artal-Villa, Hussein, et al. 2019). While some of the components of this research are similar to the work of this paper, it is still lacking in the main goal to introduce external models to

pedestrians in SUMO.

For the project mentioned above, the developers linked Unity3D to SUMO through TraCI directly. It was mentioned that usually TraaS (TraCI as a Service) is used to allow multiple types of clients to connect to SUMO, but using it as a web service introduces unacceptable delay for a driver-centric simulation. Ultimately, they implemented the TraaS library locally to avoid that side effect (Biurrun-Quel et al. 2017).

More recently, a new 3D traffic simulator is being developed in Unity3D which, like in this project, receives the vehicle data from an external source. The 3D simulation was then used to collect data through cameras, mimicking the way real autonomous vehicles collect data from its environments, significantly reducing the time and cost of its acquisition (Jin et al. 2018).

In another project, SUMO was used as the microscopic traffic to an autonomous vehicle simulator. The architecture was set to make SUMO handle general network vehicles, while USARSim was used to simulate the autonomous vehicles, using Unreal Engine to create a 3D scene of the simulation (Pereira and Rossetti 2012).

When it comes to the use of Virtual Reality (VR) to aid the creation of pedestrian models some concerns over the realism of the data collect in the virtual world are often raised. This is mainly due to the chance that test subjects may not act the same way while immersed as they do in the real world. A study into this concern have clarified that only minor differences can be found between the two scenarios (Bhagavathula et al. 2018).

This VR approach to pedestrian modelling has been used to better understand the mechanisms of microscopic pedestrian behaviour to develop a disutility minimisation model (Iryo et al. 2013). VR environments have also been used to collect data to create a model for pedestrian behaviour prediction (Costa et al. 2019).

METHODOLOGY

This section introduces the general details of the development of this project, starting with a detailed solution proposal, followed by a description of the overall system model and architecture.

Proposed Solution

As mentioned before, implementing new pedestrian models or adding new features to the existing ones in SUMO can be a cumbersome and difficult process, as it entails adding or modifying the original code base, written in C++. With this in mind, to achieve the first goal of simplifying this process, the modelling and application of the new models would need to be done externally. This would also allow different pedestrian models to coexist in SUMO, something not currently possible and necessary to fulfill the second goal of having a subject control one pedestrian.

Fortunately, SUMO can easily communicate with external application in several programming languages like C++, Python, C#, JAVA and Matlab (DLR 2020). Exploring the different interfaces for different programming languages reveals that the ones for Python and

C++ are the most developed and frequently updated. Currently, these are also the ones that include the *Person.moveToXY* method, which allows the interface to control the position of pedestrians in the network.

To facilitate the integration of new models and real people in the simulation, an interactive 3D representation of the simulation is needed. SUMO works in a 2D network, but it is necessary to transfer it to a 3D network for test subjects to feel immersed and visualize the world as they do in real life. Game engines are a popular choice to create dynamic 3D environments and, as mentioned before, Unity3D has been used in conjunction with SUMO in the past. When also considering its good integration with virtual reality and simple scripting language it became the choice for this project. Being a game engine, Unity3D also includes classes and features for path finding, which can simplify the pedestrian model creation.

In the end, the proposed solution is to connect SUMO and Unity3D to create a traffic and pedestrian simulation using the best of both software packages: the depth of traffic simulation in SUMO and the ease of use and integration of new models from Unity3D. With both working in sync, SUMO's traffic simulation influences the pedestrian simulation in Unity3D and vice-versa, creating a more complete and modular simulation.

System Architecture

The created system for the proposed solution is composed of 3 main modules: SUMO for the microscopic traffic simulation; Unity3D for the immersive visual representation and new pedestrian models; and a Python script responsible for connecting the other 2 modules. Figure 2 shows how these modules interact with each other.

The SUMO simulation module is a regular SUMO simulation with vehicles and pedestrians that follow the internal models for these categories: the default traffic model and the striping model respectively. The distinguishing factor is that it receives through TraCI the position of the pedestrians modeled from the outside in the Unity3D module. Despite being modeled

externally, they still interact with SUMO's internal inhabitants, influencing their choices in movement.

On the other end, the Unity3D module functions in reverse. It receives the position from the SUMO modeled inhabitants, and uses that information to determine the best action for the modelled pedestrians, or to influence the decision of a test subject immersed in the simulation. This module is also responsible for recreating the simulation from its 2D nature from SUMO, to a more immersive 3D environment.

Connecting these two modules is a Python script, responsible for several tasks. First, launching the SUMO simulation and establishing the TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) connection to it through TraCI. Then it opens the connection to the Unity3D visualization through a ZeroMQ TCP connection, and finally, it connects both these communication protocols.

The transmitted data varies with the intended usage of the platform. For the case demonstrated in Fig. 2, where a single pedestrian is being externally modelled or controlled by a human, all other pedestrians' and vehicles' data has to be sent from SUMO to Unity3D, with the latter only having to send this externally modelled pedestrian to SUMO. On the other hand, if all pedestrians are being simulated in Unity3D, this sends the positional data of all of them to SUMO, while SUMO only needs to transmit the positions of the vehicles. This last module, sitting between the two main modules is called the middleware.

IMPLEMENTATION - PLATFORM AND SYSTEMS

This section describes the implementation process of the discussed proposed solution. It focuses on how the road network was created and modelled, the communication protocol connecting SUMO and Unity3D, followed by how the pedestrians are controlled remotely, and finishing with the VR component of the simulation.

Network Modelling

The implementation process started with the creation of a simple SUMO scenario to test the system dur-

Fig. 2: System architecture for the platform, composed of three main modules: SUMO, the middleware and Unity3D.

Fig. 3: SUMO simulation (a) and Unity3D reconstruction (b).

ing development. Since the main focus of the system is pedestrian modelling, priority was given to spaces where they usually can be found. As such, a single lane roadway was created with walking areas on both sides and a crosswalk in the middle using SUMO’s NETEDIT¹. To populate the simulation, routes for the cars and pedestrians were created, which at runtime create new inhabitants that move to their destination following said routes.

The created network needed to be replicated in the Unity3D environment, where a scene was created by hand that matched the original scene following the data found in the *net.xml* file created by NETEDIT, which details the nodes and the edges of the network. This process could be automated, but that falls outside the scope of this work. The scale from the original SUMO network was preserved on the Unity3D side to simplify the process of transmitting coordinate and distance data between them.

Communication Protocol

To establish the communication between the two main modules, SUMO’s communication protocol TraCI was paired with ZeroMQ to enable fast and reliable message transmission between the two. This implementation of Python-Unity3D C# was based on the work by Chanchana Sornsoontorn². As mentioned before, this is being done in the middleware, since TraCI for Python has more functionalities implemented than its C# counterpart. The communication loop follows a client server model, with the middleware acting as the server and Unity3D as the client. When it starts, it waits for a message from the client. Upon receiving a message, if it includes the position of the modeled pedestrians, it uses TraCI to update their positions in SUMO. Then, it sends the position of all pedestrians and vehicles in the simulation gathered through TraCI and transmits it back to the client.

Upon receiving this message, the client updates the position and angle of the agents in the 3D world and then sends the server the position of the agents it is controlling, completing the cycle. The SUMO simulation step time is kept by the middleware, and can be

chosen between as fast as possible for simulation scenarios without humans in the loop or to keep real-time when a human subject is immersed in the simulation. This protocol is depicted in Fig. 4.

To prevent blocking of the main thread in the Unity3D simulation, which would negatively impact VR performance, the data from the server is received in a parallel thread. Due to the limitations of Unity3D, data from the simulation can only be accessed from the main thread. To bypass this, after receiving a message, it is placed in a queue of functions that are executed by the main thread when it can. This implementation was based on the work of Damian Mehers³.

At this point, it is already possible to recreate the SUMO simulation in Unity3D, as pictured in Fig. 3.

Controlling Pedestrians Through TraCI

With the communication protocol established, it is necessary to make the externally modeled pedestrians move in SUMO as well.

The *Person.moveToXY* function available in TraCI would suggest a simple solution to this, but at the time of implementation, while it can in fact move a pedestrian to any spot on the map, other pedestrians and vehicles will not become aware of its presence. This is due to the method not updating the pedestrian position in terms of edge, but only in terms of coordinates, preventing vehicles and pedestrians outside that edge to be aware of its presence.

To bypass this limitation, the message the server receives also contains the edge the pedestrians are currently at. This is calculated in Unity3D by casting a ray directly down from its position and listening to which object it intersects with. With this information, the server can detect if the pedestrian has changed edge, in which case it removes the pedestrian from the simulation and creates a copy on the current edge. While this

³Original code and information at: <https://github.com/PimDeWitte/UnityMainThreadDispatcher>

Fig. 4: Sequence diagram of communication loop between Unity3D and the middleware.

¹More details at: <https://sumo.dlr.de/docs/NETEDIT.html>

²Original code and information at: <https://github.com/off99555/Unity3D-Python-Communication>

solution can sometimes be prone to crashes, it was the only way found to circumvent SUMO’s limitations.

Another adjustment necessary for free pedestrian movement in SUMO is to make roadways available to pedestrians. Otherwise, when external pedestrians walk on the road surface outside the crosswalk the vehicles would not be aware of them and run them over.

Controlling Pedestrian in VR

The developments reported above enable achieving the goal of allowing externally controlled pedestrians in SUMO in a simple manner. In this section, we tackle the second goal of allowing real people to control one of these pedestrians, in order to study potential dangerous behaviour in a safe way.

One of the reasons that led to choosing Unity3D was due to the easy integration of virtual reality. Several Unity3D software packages exist to simplify the integration of virtual reality, with VRTK⁴ being one of the most popular. It was used to integrate SteamVR to the simulation, making it compatible with most mainstream VR systems in the market.

VRTK also includes several VR-specific locomotion methods. The typical teleport technique was not implemented as it creates unnatural motion. To maintain realism and immersion, joystick activated smooth locomotion was used, with it also being possible to rotate the camera with buttons as a fallback for when a 360° VR setup is not available. When VR is not available, it is also possible to use VRTK’s VRSimulator to control the pedestrian with keyboard and mouse.

IMPLEMENTATION - PEDESTRIAN MODEL

After implementing the general structure and functionality of this distributed simulation platform, it is still necessary to demonstrate it could indeed be used to offload pedestrian simulation from SUMO to Unity3D, to ease the implementation of new models and allow more complex models to be used. This section details the implementation of the simple and established Social Force Model for pedestrian simulation and the required adjustments to the platform to make it possible.

Multi-Agent Pedestrian Models

Many pedestrians models have been developed over the years. In the case of microscopic pedestrian simulation, it is usually achieved through the use of multi-agent systems. Two main approaches can be found in the literature, those being force-based methods in the beginning, and the more recent velocity-based methods, following different techniques such as time-to-collision or computer vision (Karamouzas et al. 2017).

While velocity-based methods more accurately simulate life-like pedestrian behaviour, they are more complex to implement and require more computational resources to run in real-time. Hence, the simpler force-based models were chosen to be implemented.

Originally, the social force model was developed by Craig Reynolds in 1987 to simulate the behaviour of flocks of birds. Each bird in the flock was simulated as a point in space where several forces (separation, alignment, and cohesion) are applied, creating a velocity vector which is then applied to the bird to update the position (Reynolds 1987).

Years later, in 1995, Helbing and Molnár took this approach to the simulation of crowds of pedestrians. For this, they based their model in 3 distinct social forces. The first, desire, emulates the want of the pedestrian to reach his destination as fast as possible, being translated as a force with the orientation and direction of the goal position. The second, repulsion, models the want of the pedestrian to keep a certain distance from other pedestrians, being calculated as the sum of the repulsion vectors in relation to other pedestrians nearby. The third one, attraction, is used to simulate the cases in which the pedestrian might want to get closer to other things, such as friendly pedestrians, a shop window or a street performer for example (Helbing and Molnár 1995).

Social Force Model Implementation in Unity3D

Before implementing the social forces model, the base for its integration in the platform was prepared.

First, the pedestrian spawner was transferred from SUMO to Unity3D. This spawner takes as input the initial number of pedestrians to spawn and the number of pedestrians to spawn per minute passed, to keep the simulation filled with pedestrians, as they are destroyed once they reach their destination.

When pedestrian agents are created, they are given a random initial location and destination on top of a

Fig. 5: Social Forces Model in action to avoid pedestrian collision. In image (a) the pedestrians are only influenced by the desire force (red). In image (b), when the pedestrians get close, the repulsive forces (blue) alter the pedestrian behaviour, resulting in the movement direction vector (green) to deviate from the desire force vector. In image (c), after avoiding collision, they return to only being commanded by the desire vector.

⁴More details at: <https://vrtoolkit.readme.io/>

sidewalk. At the same time, the pedestrian calculates the best course to reach its destination, in the form of several waypoints. To make SUMO accept the externally simulated pedestrians, the same workarounds detailed in the previous section were used. With more simulated pedestrians, the SUMO server has increased propensity to crash when a pedestrian changes edge. This is a bug that would have to be fixed in SUMO itself, in order for this platform to work reliably.

While the original implementation of the Social Forces Model was not released to the public, there is a NetLogo implementation openly available through GitHub, credited to Antoine Tordeux⁵. This implementation only takes into account the desire and repulsion forces, as the attraction force can be optional, depending on the simulation scenario. This implementation was adapted to C# and Unity3D's game engine. Figure 5 demonstrates how the modelled forces influence the pedestrian movement behaviour.

The first test showed that pedestrians tended to exit the sidewalks to avoid collisions with other pedestrians, ending up either outside the network (in the green area) or on the road, where cars circulate. To combat this issue, metaphorical walls were added to the edges of the surfaces where pedestrians can walk (sidewalks, walking areas, and crosswalks). Every simulation step, the pedestrian agent calculates the closest point on a "wall" to him and the distance to that point. When it gets close, a repulsive force with the opposite direction of the wall is added to the rest. In extreme cases where even with the repulsive force the pedestrian walked into unexpected terrain, it is forced to stay inside the lines.

SIMULATION TESTING

The developed code for this project, along with the necessary instructions, is accessible on Github⁶. All the tests were performed on Windows 10, in a machine with an Intel i7-8750h processor, an RTX 2060 graphics card and 16GB of RAM. For immersion, an Oculus Rift was used with Oculus Touch Controllers through the

⁵More details at: <https://github.com/chraibi/SocialForceModel>

⁶Codebase at: <https://github.com/dalugoga/sumo-unity-distributed-pedestrian-simulator>

Fig. 6: SUMO vehicle waiting for immersed user to cross.

SteamVR SDK (Software Development Kit).

The first step to start the simulation is to execute the middleware Python Script. The SUMO simulation will remain frozen until the Unity3D scene is played, either from the Unity3D editor or the standalone executable, making the two simulation sides synchronize and run.

Two test scenarios were created and executed, one for each implemented use scenario. The first one focuses on the VR control of a single pedestrian, while the second creates a test scenario for the social forces model.

Virtual Reality Test Scenario

A simple simulation of SUMO controlled pedestrians was created, with each pedestrian having a random start and end point. At the same time, vehicles are spawned randomly. In some cases, the pedestrians have to cross the road through a crosswalk, making the road traffic stop.

A test subject was then immersed in Unity3D with the objective of moving around and behave like a real pedestrian, trying to cross the road. To make the subject movement be represented in SUMO, his camera movement and rotation were tied to a SUMO pedestrian, now being controlled by TraCI with the inputs from Unity3D being fed through ZeroMQ.

The inputs from this pedestrians were correctly transmitted to SUMO, making the other pedestrians and vehicles respond to its presence in the simulation. This environment was very immersive for the test user with no noticeable delays or simulation inconsistencies. Figure 6 shows the subject waiting for the red car to see him and stop, before initiating the crossing safely.

Simulating all Pedestrians Externally

To test the feasibility of completely offloading the simulation of pedestrians to Unity3D, a new scenario was created, where Unity3D itself spawns, removes and controls the actions of dozens of pedestrians simultaneously. In this test, 100 pedestrians are initially created, with 5 more added each minute, to keep the pedestrian population high. In this scenario, SUMO is only handling the simulation of cars, also randomly spawned.

This simulation scenario ran without major problems, with pedestrians moving at a regular pace the majority of the time. In simple collision scenarios between 2 or 3 pedestrians, the social forces model does a good job at keeping the flow in a human-like manner. However, when the pedestrian density increases, mostly around the crosswalk area, the age of the model becomes apparent, as some pedestrians are forced to wait for a chance to move forward, or even backtrack to find a better position to move forward.

Despite these problems, the most important requirements were still met. A large pedestrian crowd was successfully externally simulated in Unity3D to be used by SUMO, while the vehicles being modelled by SUMO were still aware of their presence and would stop to let the pedestrians cross the road. Figure 7 shows the two simulation representations synchronized while running the Social Forces Model.

Fig. 7: Unity3D’s (a) externally simulated pedestrian agents being replicated in SUMO (b).

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

An extension to the SUMO microscopic traffic simulator was developed that simplifies the process of integrating externally controlled pedestrians, with both objectives being achieved. Using TraCI, SUMO was connected to the Unity3D game engine to create a 3D representation of the simulation and provide information to new pedestrian models. It also allows for real people to be incorporated in the simulation through immersive virtual reality headsets. The end result allows researchers to develop more complex pedestrian models for SUMO and to safely study the behaviour of real people in the role of pedestrians.

For future work, it would be important to implement a modern pedestrian model that simulates pedestrians in a even more realistic way, with it being possible for them to jaywalk, use the crosswalk while it indicates not to cross, etc. By introducing this potential risk behaviours, studies could be performed to help understand them and ways to prevent accidents from happening. This model could be created from data collected from immersed users and verified with other user tests in the platform. It would also be fundamental to fix the problems related with how the external pedestrians are controlled in SUMO to prevent the seemingly random crashes and increase the platform’s stability.

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